

doi:10.5281/zenodo.14987761

Factors Of Depression Among People Living With HIV/AIDS In Port Harcourt And Obio/Akpo Local Government Areas Of Rivers State

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ABSTRACT

The study investigated gender and one's level of education as factors of depression among people living with HIV/AIDS in Port-Harcourt and Obio/Akpor Local Government Areas of Rivers State. The objective was to find out the level of influence of Gender and Level of Education on depression among this group. The study adopted Ex-Post facto designs. Three hundred and fifty (350) HIV/AIDS patients were selected using the Accidental Sampling Method from both University of Port-Harcourt Teaching Hospital (U.P.T.H) and Braith-Whait Memorial Specialist Hospital (B.M.S.H) now Rivers State University Teaching Hospital (RSUTH) Port-Harcourt. Two Research Questions and Two Null Hypothesis were formulated to guide the study. Two Instruments which were the Correlates of Depression Questionnaire (C.D.Q) and HIV/AIDS Patients Depression Inventory (HDI) were used. Reliability of both Instruments were determined by giving them to 30 Patients who were not part of the sample. For CDQ, a sectional reliability of 0.53, 0.84 and 0.89 were established, while for HDI, a reliability index of 0.91 was established. Simple Regression was used to Analyze Data and findings were that Gender ($p=0.034<0.05$) has significant influence on depression while Level of Education ($p=0.725>0.05$) has no significant influence on depression among HIV/AIDS patients in Port-Harcourt and Obio/Akpo L.G.As of Rivers State. It was recommended among others that Government and mainly Counselors should focus more on counseling the patients. Based on the limitations, suggestions for further studies were made as well as contribution of the study to knowledge base.

Key words: Gender, Level of Education, Positivity.

INTRODUCTION

HIV means Human Immunodeficiency Virus (infection) while AIDS means Acquired Immunodeficiency Syndrome (disease). AIDS is a disease of the human immune system caused by infection with Human Immunodeficiency Virus HIV (WHO, 2007). During the initial infection, a person may experience a brief period of influenza-like illness. This is typically followed by a prolonged period without symptoms. As the illness progresses it interferes more and more with the immune system, making the person much more likely to get infections, including opportunistic infections and tumors that do not usually affect people who have normal immune systems. (Ibulu 2014)

HIV is transmitted primarily through unprotected sexual intercourse (including anal and oral sex), contaminated blood transfusions, hypodermic needles, and from mother to child during pregnancy, delivery, or breastfeeding. Some bodily fluids, such as saliva and tears, do not transmit HIV. Prevention of HIV infection, primarily through safe sex and needle-exchange programs, are key strategies to control the spread of the disease. There is no cure or vaccine, however, antiretroviral treatment can slow the course of the disease, these medications are expensive and may be associated with side effect (WHO, 2007). When HIV develops to full blown AIDS, the patient manifests a number of signs and symptoms. The signs and symptoms are different in terms of severity in individuals. The signs and symptoms include: Gradual Weights loss, Prolonged fever, Prolonged cough, Prolonged diarrhoea that does not respond to medical treatment, Skin rashes etc.

HIV/AIDS has biological/health effects as well as psychological and social effects. The biological/health and the psychological effects stress the health and psychological consequences of the disease on the victim respectively while the social effects stress the consequences on the larger society. HIV/AIDS is a terminal disease and its patients face imminent death. It shortens people's life. HIV/AIDS also weakens one's immune system and makes one unproductive. (Agbakwuru and Ekechukwu 2009).

Psychologically, the effects of HIV/AIDS include anxiety, anger, frustrations, and guilt feelings. The diagnosis of HIV/AIDS is normally accompanied by feelings of anxiety, anger, frustrations and guilt. Results of a positive diagnosis thrusts sever uncertainty into one's life. Initially, the individual tries to cope with these psychological feelings by denial of the result of the test. However, this defense mechanism does not remove the disease. As the reality of the result of the test dawns on the individual, the thought of pains to be experienced and the impending loss of control over one's life that overwhelms the individual leads to dysphoria. This is a feeling of unhappiness that hangs over one like a cloud of impending doom. It gives birth to depression in the lives of people living with HIV/AIDS. Agbakwuru and Ekechukwu (2009). Closely related to the feelings of anxiety, anger and frustrations are the feelings of worthlessness, inadequacy, despair and emptiness. These negative psychological effects of the disease on the patient are the direct result of three major factors namely (a) The worsening condition of the patient, loss of independence and sense of self-control (b) The knowledge of economic and social losses as well as (3) The impending loss of one's own life. These in turn lead to a decline in the individual's level of self-concept and depression. The later stage of AIDS also leads to social isolation and loneliness. Agbakwuru and Ekechukwu (2009).

Socially, HIV/AIDS has economic effects on personal, family and national economy. The care and management of the patients drains the economy of families and states. This dependence on others for care and management serves as a major source of stress not only to the HIV/AIDS patients but also to their families and significant others. In fact, the emotional impact of this alone is very destabilizing and poses a very bitter pill for most family members and significant others to swallow. Agbakwuru and Ekechukwu (2009). From this same source they say, being infected of HIV/AIDS by any member of the family alters the entire social responsibility and relationship. For instance, getting infected of HIV/AIDS by the father who is normally the major breadwinner alters the normal pattern of social responsibility in the family and thus, forces the wife or the children to assume the role of the family breadwinner.

HIV/AIDS is a deadly disease without any known cure. However, one can avoid it by (a) Abstaining entirely from sexual intercourse outside marriage. (b) Having exclusive sexual intercourse with a faithfully partner. (3) Avoiding the habit of sharing needles for intravenous drug use. (4) Consistent and correct use of condom.

Mother to Child Transmission (M T C T): A mother can transmit HIV infection to her child during pregnancy, labour/delivery, or through breastfeeding. The risk of Mother to Child Transmission of HIV varies from one country to another (Orupabo, 2006). Beyond the risk of transmission during pregnancy and childbirth, prolonged breastfeeding adds a risk of 15% or more, depending on duration and other factors that scientists are still trying to understand. The risk of MTCT increases if a woman becomes infected before /during pregnancy or if she becomes ill with AIDS because of the viral loads. Other factors that increase the opportunity for transmission during this period include viral, bacteria, or parasitic

infections. Most infants who acquire HIV during delivery do so through exposure to maternal blood or cervical secretions that contain HIV. Prolonged membrane rupture and invasive delivery techniques have also been associated with higher risks of MTCT during labour and delivery. Orupabo, (2006). The danger of MTCT is less when HIV positive mother exclusively breastfeed for the first six month. However, there is increased risk of transmission with mixed feeding and complications developing from poor breastfeeding techniques e.g mastitis, cracked and bloody nipples. The risk of MTCT also increases if the mother becomes infected with HIV while breastfeeding, as viral load in the initial stage of infection is very high.

Prevention of Mother to Child Transmission: Currently, there is a four pronged approach towards reducing the risk of MTCT as enumerated below: (1) Prevention of primary infection in women. (2) Avoidance of unintended pregnancies in HIV infected women. (3) Prevention of transmission from HIV infected women to their infants. (4) Follow-up care and support.

Pathophysiology of HIV/AIDS: It is how the virus destroys the white blood cells to bring about total breakdown of the immune system in humans. According to Oyeokue as cited in Onukwufor (2012) the HIV/AIDS is a disease that slowly and steadily destroys the body's immune system. The immune system is a collection of cells and organs that work together to defend the body from germs or substances (antigens) which may cause illnesses. The immune system composed of T-lymphocytes and B-lymphocytes that play the role of the defending army. B-lymphocytes are responsible for the production of antibodies. Antibody is a substance that your body produces in your blood to fight illnesses and infections, it is an important part of the immune system that protects your body against disease. Among the T-lymphocytes are carriers of CD4 receptors. These are the T-lymphocytes or CD4 + cells. HIV infects a person's CD4 T-cells and uses these cells to replicate itself. In a person infected with HIV, CD4 cells are progressively destroyed. (Orupabo, 2006). As these cells are destroyed, the person's immune system is weakened, and the person is more likely to develop an opportunistic infection. When a certain number of CD4 cells have been destroyed, the immune system loses its ability to fight off other infections. The person then becomes more vulnerable to opportunistic infections (e.g tuberculosis, toxoplasmosis, and candidiasis) and is more prone to develop certain cancers. (Orupabo, 2006).

Window Period in HIV/AIDS: This is an initial stage of the virus, when the effect of the disease has not manifested usually the first six months of contracting it. However one can unknowingly transmit it.

Laboratory Diagnosis of HIV: The diagnosis of HIV infection is usually made based on the detection of antibodies to the virus. Most often, the body fluid tested is blood. Antibody test rarely 100 percent sensitive (i.e able to correctly categorize an infected person as positive) and specific (i.e able to correctly categorize a non-infected person as negative). Therefore, united nations on aids (UNAIDS), world health organization (WHO) and center for disease control (CDC) jointly recommend that all positive test results should be confirmed by testing, preferably using a different test methods.

Pre-Test And Post-Test Counseling: Counseling in relation to HIV/AIDS is a confidential dialogue between a person and a care provider aimed at enabling the person cope with stress and make informed personal decisions related to HIV/AIDS.(WHO1995).

Benefits of HIV pre-test counseling. It helps the patient and the health care provider to identify risk factors and symptoms that may indicate the patient is infected. It helps the patient to anticipate the possible HIV positive test result and begin to consider how he/she would respond to such result. It provides information regarding HIV transmission and risk reduction behaviours. **Benefits of HIV post-test counseling.** It clarifies that the test detected HIV antibodies and that means the person is infected. It discusses fears about disclosing diagnosis. It helps the patient to recognize positive coping skills. It provides information on support network and groups etc.

Why HIV Counseling Is Important: HIV/AIDS is a uniquely stigmatized disease. Stigma affects every aspect of providing medical and social care to people at risk of and infected with HIV. This stigma prevents people who have received positive test results from accepting them, seeking appropriate treatment, and implementing risk reduction strategies to prevent transmission to others. One of the aims

of HIV counseling is to reduce internalized stigma by providing information about HIV/AIDS in a neutral and non-judgmental manner.

According to Nwankwo (2015), Depression is a mood disorder. It is more than sadness or grief. Depression is sadness or grief that is more intense and lasts longer than it should. It has various causes: eg events in the daily life, chemical changes in the brain, a side effect of medications and several physical disorders. About 5% to 10% of the general population gets depressed. However, rates of depression in people with HIV are as high as 60%. Women with HIV are twice as likely as men to be depressed (Osinkwa, 2014). Symptoms of depression vary from person to person. Most health care providers suspect depression if patients report feeling blue or having very little interest in daily activities. If these feelings go on for two weeks or longer, and the patient also has some of the following symptoms, they are probably depressed (Lekan, 2013). (1) Fatigue or feeling slow and sluggish. (2) Problems concentrating. (3) Low sex drive. (4) Problems sleeping; waking very early or excessive sleeping. (5) Feeling guilty, worthless, or hopeless. (6) Decreased appetite or weight loss. (7) Overeating.

There are many causes of depression. Having the diagnosis of a chronic disease, like HIV infection or AIDS, can make depressive symptoms worse. Some medications used to treat HIV can cause or worsen depression. Diseases such as anemia or diabetes can cause symptoms that look like depression. So can drug use, or low levels of testosterone, vitamin B6, or vitamin B12.

People who are infected with both HIV and hepatitis B or C are more likely to be depressed, especially if they are being treated with interferon (Shelly, 2006). Other risk factors include: being female, having a personal or family history of mental illness, alcohol and substance abuse, not having enough social support, not telling others you are HIV-positive, treatment failure (HIV or other). The presence of Depression in an individual's life can lead him/her to diminish interest in social activities, feeling of detachment from others, suppressed emotional feelings and a sense that the future is bleak and empty (Lekan, 2013). Depressed HIV/AIDS patients have longer hospital stay and are more often discharged from hospital to nursing homes than other patients. They show less motivation to undergo rehabilitation, take their drugs, keep to appointment etc, and they are less likely to restore their quality of life. Depression over illness and treatment have also be linked to suicide among people living with HIV/AIDS (Shelly, 2006). HIV is a chronic and life threatening illness and like such other illnesses can be stressful to manage, its life-threatening nature may instigate fear of impending mortality. Moreover, the medical sequelae of HIV infection, its associated opportunistic infections and side effects of antiretroviral treatment can mimic symptoms of depression.

People with depression have impaired mental health functioning, they also tend to generally have a poor physical health (Razyfert, 2000). The HIV/AIDS patients, males and females, are people with different social, economic, psychological, educational and personality backgrounds, so the researchers have presumed that variations in depression among people living with HIV/AIDS may be as a result of social, economic, psychological, academic factors which include mostly Gender and Level of Education. The correlates of depression in this study are

Gender and One's Level of Education.

Gender refers to socially defined and learned male and female behaviours that shape the opportunities that one is offered in life, the roles one may play and the kind of relationship one keeps. It is distinct from sex, which is a biologically determined and fixed set of characteristics for men and women. It is also distinct from though closely linked to sexuality, which is the "social construction of a biological drive" that is defined by how, why and with whom one has sex (Rao Gupta, 2000). Gender affects masculinity and femininity roles, status, norms and values, responsibilities and expectations, sexuality, division of labour, power, distribution of resources and rewards. Gender roles dictate how each of the above factors differ between men and women. Since gender is a social construct, the differences between men and women may vary from place to place, but they are almost always present and ultimately have a significant impact on vulnerability to HIV/AIDS. The inequalities between men and women that are created and reinforced by gender roles typically leave women especially vulnerable to HIV infection and its impact. But it is also important to recognize that gender roles affect men's vulnerability as well. As a result of their societal

roles, women and girls face a number of unique challenges that affect their ability to protect themselves from HIV/AIDS and its overwhelming effects.

Social norms about female sexuality make it very difficult for women and girls around the world to protect themselves from HIV infection. Women and girls are often encouraged to remain uninformed about sexual matters and/or remain sexually passive. Traditional norms of virginity for unmarried girls impede young women's freedom to seek important sexual health information, including knowledge about HIV risk. The expectations for sexual passivity in women, along with the priority given to male sexual pleasure, also makes it difficult for women to be an equal partner in deciding the terms of sexual activity, including negotiating safer sex practices.

The power imbalance between men and women also translates into economic dependency for women. In most societies, men have greater control and access to productive resources. Women may feel pressured to stay in risky or abusive relationships with men because of the economic consequences of leaving. Limited income-earning opportunities are a common challenge for girls and women around the world. Women may be forced to exchange sexual favours for money or gifts in order to meet their basic needs, support their families, pay for school fees, or even to enhance their social power. Sex is therefore used as a commodity and a survival strategy, and such 'transactional sex' most often takes place with older men (who are more likely to be HIV positive).

Societal expectations of men and boys also have an impact on male vulnerability to HIV/AIDS. Social norms about masculinity often assume that men are knowledgeable and experienced when it comes to sexual issues. This can have the negative effect of preventing men from seeking sexual health information or admitting their lack of knowledge about HIV risk reduction. However, male and female individuals may differ in terms of their interest, aptitude, adjustment, need, attitude even in their responsibilities. The fact that one is a male, saddled with the responsibility of taking care of his family and now being infected with HIV/AIDS may contribute to depression in the life of that patient mainly when one is the bread winner of their family.

Ditlevsen & Elklit (2012) looked at gender differences in adherence to treatment and illness behaviour in HIV/AIDS patients. An explanatory study in Spain. The study analyzed the gender differences in adherence to treatment and illness behaviour of HIV/AIDS patients. The sample consist of 69 HIV patients, taking HIV/AIDS Anti-Retroviral Therapy (HAART), obtained at the Castellon General Hospital Internal Medical Service. The researchers evaluated, not only the variable directly linked with the adherence such as the patient report about the change of risk behaviours, the compliance with the drug treatment and the assistance to the medical appointment, but also other illness behaviour variables that can be related such as the patients assessment about the illness seriousness, his/her expectations about the treatment or his/her relationship with the doctor. In general, the result do not show significant statistical differences between men and women. Significant differences are obtained in only 6% of variables, especially in some risk factors and in belief (higher in women) that antiretroviral treatment will be completely ineffective. Logistic regression analysis did not evidence that gender contribute to predict adherence.

Education is a universal practice or phenomenon engaged in all societies at all ages of development. It is described as the total processes of human learning by which knowledge is impacted, valued skills developed and faculties trained. Fafunwa in kosemani (2002) defined education as a process by which a young child or adult develops the ability and other behavioural forms which are of positive or acceptable value to the society in which he lives. Education frees one's mind there by allowing one to think beyond what one is told. This points clearly to the fact that education is the process that impacts useful and relevant skills to individuals there by enhancing the growth of the society. In essence, it prepares the human mind to enable it cope in future challenges. Level of education in HIV/AIDS positivity matters so much in the lives of HIV/AIDS patients, in other to understand the influence between education and HIV/AIDS two questions are of interest. (1) What is it about educated people that enables them to change their behaviour in response to the epidemic? (2) What aspects of behaviour change are responsible for the reduction in HIV prevalence among this group? The increase in knowledge, understanding or self-efficacy that comes with education is responsible for behaviour change (De Walgue, 2002). According to

Mathew and Kamal (2005), education is associated with higher HIV prevalence in the early stages of an epidemic, in the later stages more educated individuals have less risky sexual behaviour and are less likely to be HIV positive. Poor education is often implied as a reason why adherence is unlikely to be high in sub-sahara Africa. (Horries, Nyangulu, Hergreaves, Kaluwa & Salamiponi, 2001). They also agreed that adherence is perceived as a significant barrier to the delivery of Anti-Retroviral Therapy (ART) in sub-sahara Africa in particular. Here they view the evidence that education and literacy are related to treatment adherence. In summary, it is clear that education has a role to play in HIV/AIDS situation. An educated person though being HIV positive, can easily understand the essence of treatment adherence, counseling etc, education helps one to know that even in HIV positivity, there is still hope for the future.

Onyenaso (2014), carried out a study on psychosocial factor and level of education as correlates of anxiety and depression among people living with HIV/AIDS in Enugu State. An ex-post facto design was used by the researcher to carry out the study. A sample of 350 HIV/AIDS patient were selected using Accidental sampling technique for the study. An instrument called psychosocial factors inventory (PFI) and HIV/AIDS Anxiety and Depression Questionnaire (HADQ) were used to collect data for the study. Mean, ANOVA, Standard deviation and multiple regression analyses were used to analyze data generated by (PFI) and (HADQ). The researcher found out that level of education, which was one of the variables of the study has no significant relationship with depression among HIV/AIDS patients Enugu State.

The researchers being a health worker and a lecturer have noticed that the rate at which the people living with HIV/AIDS mainly in Port-Harcourt and Obio/Akpo Local Government Areas of Rivers State are being depressed calls for urgent attention on the causes of such depression and solutions proffered. Most of them who are responsible citizens of this country are now battling with their health conditions. Some of them are bread winners of their families, have brighter futures but can no longer think far as in planning ahead as a result of a disease that has no known cure. At times they reflect on their health conditions with negative feelings which in extension affect their productivities in their places of work, their quality of life, their future and entire life negatively. This scenario makes them at times, not to strive to achieve things that they will enjoy in future since they have the mentality of death coming very soon. This situation leads to a decline in the rate of production which in turn affects the national income. It also drains the economy of this country in the area of provision of health facilities, antiretroviral drugs, health workers which the government makes available. The problem of this study therefore is, as every individual differs from one another in terms of reaction to a threatening situation, so also people living with HIV/AIDS. HIV/AIDS having known as a disease that has no known cure and the imminent death awaits the patient, the presence of depression becomes inevitable in the lives of those living with HIV/AIDS so also the level of depression may differ from one person to the other as a result of certain factors (gender and level of education) in their lives. The extent to which these factors influence depression among people living with HIV/AIDS was not certain. It is for these reasons that the researchers tend to carry out this study so as to determine the extent to which these factors influence depression among people living with HIV/AIDS in Port-Harcourt and Obio/Akpo Local Government Area of Rivers State. In specific terms, this study was designed to:

- (1) Find out the influence of gender on depression among people living with HIV/AIDS in Port Harcourt and Obio/Akpor Local Government Areas of Rivers State.
- (2) Ascertain the influence of one's level of education on depression among people living with HIV/AIDS in Port Harcourt and Obio/Akpor Local Government Areas of Rivers State.

The following research questions guided the study in the realization of its set objectives.

- (1) What influence does gender have on depression among people living with HIV/AIDS in Port Harcourt and Obio/Akpor Local Government Areas of Rivers State?
- (2) What influence does one's level of education have on depression among people living with HIV/AIDS in Port Harcourt and Obio/Akpor Local Government Areas of Rivers State?

These null hypotheses were also tested at 0.05 level of significance.

- Ho₁: There was no significant influence of gender on depression among people living with HIV/AIDS in Port Harcourt and Obio/Akpor Local Government Areas of Rivers State.
- Ho₂: There was no significant influence of level of education on depression among people living with HIV/AIDS in Port Harcourt and Obio/Akpor Local Government Areas of Rivers State.

METHOD

The name of the research design adopted for this study is ex-post facto. The population of the study consisted of all the HIV/AIDS out patients in University of Port Harcourt Teaching Hospital (UPTH) and Braith-Whaite Memorial Specialist Hospital (BMSH). A sample of 350 HIV/AIDS patients (175 from UPTH and 175 from BMSH). Two instruments were used for data collection: namely Correlates of Depression Questionnaire (C.D.Q) and HIV/AIDS patient depression inventory (HDI). The CDQ was a four point likert type scale with two sections A and B. Section A was used to elicit information on the personal data of the subjects such as gender and level of education. Section B of the CDQ had 30 items which were used to measure the correlates of depression. The HDI is a four point likert scale and has 20 items which measured depression. Face and content validities of the instruments were determined by experts in Educational Psychology, Measurement and Evaluation. The reliability of the instruments were determined through test retest method. 30 HIV/AIDS Patients were drawn using accidental sampling technique for the reliability test. The following coefficient were obtained from the instruments correlates of depression questionnaire (CDQ). Fear of death 0.68, Guilt 0.83 and stigmatization 0.84, HIV/AIDS patient depression inventory (HDI) 0.91. The coefficient values were considered high enough to use the instruments as reliable tools for obtaining data for this study. Mean (\bar{x}) and standard deviation (SD) were used to answer the research questions while the null hypotheses were tested using simple regression, t-test and ANOVA at 0.05 level of significance.

RESULTS

The results of statistical analysis are presented in the following tables.

Table 1: Independent t-test analysis of the influence of gender on depression among HIV/AIDS patients in Port Harcourt and Obio/Akpor.

Gender	N	\bar{X}	S.D	Df	t-cal	α	Sig.	Result
Male	150	40.79	19.26					
Female	200	36.83	13.98	348	2.130	0.05	0.034	Significant (Reject Ho)

From the analysis in Table 1, males were 150, while females were 200. Mean and standard deviation values for males were 40.79 and 19.26 respectively, while for female were 36.83 and 13.98 respectively. From their mean values, it could be deduced that male HIV/AIDS patients are more depressed than their female counterparts who had less mean scores. Calculated $t = 2.130$ with sig. value = 0.034. Hence, since sig value ($p = 0.034 < 0.05$) is less than 0.05 alpha level, at 198 degrees of freedom, the null hypothesis was rejected and the alternate accepted, meaning that gender has a significant influence on depression among HIV/AIDS patients in Obio/Akpor Local Government Area of Rivers State.

Table 2: Influence of one's level of education on depression among HIV/AIDS patients.

Level of education	N	\bar{x}	SD				
WAEC	150	36.06	18.38				
HND	116	37.92	18.88				
B.Sc & above	84	36.81	19.87				
Analysis of Variance							
	Sum Of sq.	d.f	Mean Sq	F	α	Sig.	Result
Between Group	230.609	2	115.304				
Within group	124116.321	347	357.684	0.322	0.05	0.725	Insignificant (Reject Ho)
Total	124346.929	349					

The analysis in Table 2 reveals N for WAEC, HND and B.Sc group to be 150, 116 and 84 respectively. Means and standard deviations were 36.06, 18.38, 37.92, 18.88; and 36.81, 19.87 respectively. From their mean values, it is evidenced that those in the B.Sc and above group experience high level of depression, followed by those with WAEC and lastly by those with HND. Mean square were 115.304 and 357.684 respectively. $F = 0.322$ with significance value = 0.725. Hence, since sig value ($p = 0.725 > 0.05$) is greater than 0.05 chosen alpha, the null hypothesis is accepted, meaning that level of education has no significant influence on depression among HIV/AIDS patients in Port Harcourt and Obio/Akpor Local Government Area.

DISCUSSION OF FINDINGS

From researchers finding one, it is revealed that gender has a significant influence on depression among HIV/AIDS patients. This result or finding implies that HIV/AIDS patients could be depressed or not depressed depending on their gender. It means specifically that male patients do feel depressed more than their female counterparts. This result could come because of the psychological as well as societal expectation placed on each category of the gender. For instance, it is widely believed that men or males are the bread winners of the family. Based on this, it is perceived that if something happens to them, then it will affect their families more. Hence, the result indicating that males are more depressed could be because they have channeled all their effort in contemplating how they have failed their families instead of thinking on how to move ahead. On the other hand, the result is surprising to the researchers because females which are generally (although it may be wrong) seen as weaker vessels should be the one that such affects most and not the males. This finding however is in line with that reported by Jonathan (2012) who noted that gender has a significant relationship with depression among people living with HIV/AIDS.

From research finding two revealed that one's level of education has no significant influence on depression among HIV/AIDS patients in Port Harcourt city and Obio/Akpor Local Government Area. This result means that the academic height one attain cannot make him to be depressed neither will it make him not to be depressed if he acquires the virus. The finding clearly suggest that there are some events in which one's level of education cannot prove to be a decisive factor. It means that even individual who acquires a Ph.D degree or WAEC could be equally depressed depending on his/her own perception of the event. This finding could actually come because people are quite aware of the fact that HIV/AIDS has no respect for any person, both rich, poor, old, young, alike could be affected. This however is in contrast with that reported earlier by Ibulu (2014) who noted that one's level of education has a significant influence on depression among HIV/AIDS patients in Obio/Akpor.

CONCLUSION

Conclusively, the study revealed that gender significantly influence depression among people living with HIV/AIDS in Port Harcourt City and Obio/Akpor Local Government Areas of Rivers State. On the other hand, the study has it that one's level of education did not influence depression among people living with HIV/AIDS in Port Harcourt City and Obio/Akpor Local Government Areas of Rivers State. The researchers concluded by saying that if the recommendations are being implemented, the level of depression in the lives of those living with HIV/AIDS in Port Harcourt City and Obio/Akpor Local Government Areas of Rivers State will be reduced to the barest minimum.

RECOMMENDATIONS

Based on the findings of the study, the following recommendations were made:

1. Adequate concentration should be paid to male patients in order to know that even with their condition, they can still provide, care and carry out their responsibilities as men.
2. All patients not minding their educational status should subject themselves to counselling services. This will help in reducing depression among the various social class and give them a sense of hope towards moving ahead.

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